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Ryanair Customer Experience Analysis: Findings and Recommendations Based on 100 Online Reviews

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ABSTRACT

In today's airline industry, understanding what customers think is very important for success. Airlines need to know if passengers are happy with their services. This report looks at recent online comments and reviews to understand how customers feel about Ryanair and to find ways the airline can improve. It is examined that the newest 100 comments from Skytrax. The aim is to find out if their customers are happy or not with the services of Ryanair.

The study puts these comments into three groups: positive, negative, and neutral. It also looks at the main things customers talk about, like how the airline helps them or if flights arrive late. It will help the airline understand which of its actions are good which need improvement.

From these findings, in the report there will be suggestions to help Ryanair to make its services better. This work helps understand what customers think and how the airline can improve their customer's experience.

Keywords: Ryanair, customer reviews, sentiment analysis

1.INTRODUCTION

It is very important for airlines to know if their customers are happy. When people have good flights, they often choose to fly with the same airline again. As noted by Hennig-Thurau et al. (2002), understanding relationship marketing outcomes involves integrating relational benefits and relationship quality, which are crucial for customer retention. Today, many people write about their experiences with airlines online. They use websites like Twitter

and Skytrax to share what they think. This report aims to understand what customers think of Ryanair. The study looks at the newest 100 comments from Skytrax that people wrote about this airline online.

The comments are read to see if they are mostly happy, mostly unhappy, or just okay. This is called looking at the "feeling" of the comments. In this report it is also examined that what people were talking about. For example, some

Case Study

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people might talk about the staff on the plane, while others might talk about if their flight was on time. By doing this, it can be found out what Ryanair is doing well and what needs to be improved. In the findings section of this report, some simple ideas will be given to help Ryanair to improve their service for their customers.

2.METHODOLOGY

To create this report, information was collected from the Skytrax website. Skytrax is a website where passengers can write reviews and talk about their experiences with airline's flights. The reviews for Ryanair were used for this study. The 100 most recent reviews written by customers were collected and analyzed. All these information was collected in April 2025.

These 100 reviews classified and analyzed carefully. After classifying them, the main ideas and feelings in each review were noted. All this information was then put into a table using Microsoft Excel. Average score for Ryanair is calculated and sentiment analysis was performed. This helped to organize the reviews and make it easier to see if the customers were mostly happy or unhappy with Ryanair. The table also used to create pie chart and to group the reviews based on what the customers were talking about, such as the staff, the seats, or the flights themselves.

3.FINDINGS

After looking at all the comments, it was seen what people were talking about the most. A lot of people (31 comments) had no problems, so this group is called 'No Issues'. The next biggest thing people talked about was 'Customer

Service' (20 comments). This shows that many people wrote about their experience with the airline staff. Also, "Pricing & Hidden Fees" was talked about a lot (15 comments). Other problems that people mentioned were "Check-in & Boarding" (9 comments), "Flight Delays & Cancellations" (9 comments), "Baggage Issues" (8 comments), and "In-Flight Experience" (6 comments). Not many people talked about "Overbooking" (2 comments). Figure 1 shows a clear picture of how many comments were about each of these topics. Additionally, all mentioned Skytrax customer reviews are included as screenshots in the appendices section with their respective categories.

Fig. 1. Pie chart showing the distribution of complaint categories

The comments were also looked at to see how people felt when they wrote them by categorizing them as shown in Figure 2. Most people felt negative. There were 67 comments

Ryanair can make sure bags are not lost. They can use tags on bags that are easy to see. Also, more people can help put bags on and take them off the plane carefully. This will stop bags from getting lost or broken.

3.1.5. Ensure basic cleanliness of aircraft

Ryanair should make sure their planes are clean inside. This means cleaning the chairs and the little tables. They should also check the toilets to make sure they are clean for everyone to use.

4. CONCLUSION

In this report it is analyzed that what people think about Ryanair. In most of the comments customers were not happy. Many customers wrote negative reviews online in Skytrax. The average score given by customers was also too low for a one of the most known low cost carriers. This shows that many people who fly with Ryanair are not very satisfied now. If customers are not happy, they might choose to fly with other airlines next time. This can be devastating for Ryanair because they could lose customers. It is important for Ryanair to listen to what their customers are saying in these comments. They need to try and make things better so that people have a better experience when they fly.

If Ryanair makes the changes suggested in this report, like helping customers more and being clear about prices, then maybe more people will be happy with them. Happy customers might fly

with Ryanair again and tell their friends to fly with them too. This can help Ryanair be more successful in the future.

5. REFERENCES

Hennig-Thurau, T., Gwinner, K. P., & Gremler, D. D. (2002). *Understanding relationship marketing outcomes: An integration of relational benefits and relationship quality*. *Journal of Service Research*, 4(3), 230–247. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094670502004003006>

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6. APPENDICES

6.1. POSITIVE FEEDBACK SCREENSHOTS

8/10 "pleasant and uneventful flights"
E Karalovich (Belarus) 10th September 2024

Trip Verified | Cologne to Corfu return. As usually in my experience with Ryanair, pleasant and uneventful flights. Very smooth and quick check-in and boarding. The flight to Corfu was slightly late because of overloaded Corfu airport, but nothing critical, the return flight was punctual. The cabin crew very attentive and polite. This time the aircraft was a newer Boeing 737-8 MAX and I need to admit that the seats are cramped a bit in comparison to older Boeings. The price was quite high (but still cheaper than the competitors) but that's expected because of the leisure destination during the high season. Generally I have no major objections and will definitely choose Ryanair again.

Aircraft	Boeing 737-8 MAX
Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Cologne to Corfu
Date Flown	September 2024
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

8/10 "a good performance"
C Barton (United Kingdom) 3rd September 2024

Trip Verified | I shall begin by stating that I am impressed with the manner in which Ryanair communicates with it's customers. From the moment I booked the flight to a day before the journey, I received a number of reminders and communications from Ryanair. At Eindhoven Airport, Ryanair staff managed the queue rather well in that priority customers were honoured and boarded the flight first. Although this was a short flight of around 1 hour, it was very busy with the end of the school holidays. The flight was full and some of the passengers were not easy for the crew to cope with. Blissfully, the staff took the safety demonstration seriously and tried to cope with certain passengers trying to take too much hand luggage onto the flight. The crew worked hard and offered a drinks service. There was a slight delay to the flight but this was fine. It was a disappointment that the captain did not make announcements. The price paid was reasonable for the time of the year. Overall, a good performance from Ryanair!

Aircraft	Boeing 737 Max
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Eindhoven to London Stansted
Date Flown	September 2024
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Food & Beverages	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

7/10

"boarding process is a concern"

C Barton (United Kingdom) 10th August 2024

Trip Verified | There are lots of positives to write about for this flight, Ryanair kept me well informed and updated before the flight with emails and as long as one follows the rules there are no problems! Luton is a bit awkward to get to but I find this airport to be efficient. The check-in agent was very friendly and efficient and it paid to get to the airport extra early. My gripe was that the boarding process did not respect the priority and non-priority ticketed passengers. There was a very steep set of steps to negotiate and I saw several people with babies and toddlers struggling but above all 2 elderly people were finding this very troublesome and were only assisted by other passengers. No cabin crew greeted the passengers. The captain was informative and helpful in that he made some announcements and welcomed passengers aboard the flight. This was a short flight of just over 1 hour, the cabin crew worked hard at selling items. Disembarkation was also efficient. On this flight Ryanair did rather well - the boarding process is a concern and one would expect assistance for elderly folks when needed.

Aircraft	Boeing 737
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Luton to Cork
Date Flown	August 2024
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Food & Beverages	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

7/10

"Overall a good experience"

C Barton (United Kingdom) 10th August 2024

Trip Verified | Check-in at Cork Airport was awful! I arrived 3 hours before my scheduled flight and the check-in counter had 4 people sitting in a huddle two of them speaking in an Eastern European language while passengers were kept waiting. There were also a few machines to self-check in and bag drop but a person would need a mobile phone with QR software and wifi connection to use it. This excluded a large number of people, the person overseeing this had a poor grasp of English. I had prepaid for extra luggage and needed to check-it in, the agent did not even speak to me and did not have the manners to respond to a simple "good morning" her abrupt manner was not acceptable. I saw her behave in a similar manner towards other passengers. Boarding was actually efficiently managed. One member of the cabin-crew was very proactive and seemed to be doing the work of several people. The young male staff member in question was superb and had a very nice rapport with children and I saw him help a visually impaired lady to her seat. More than that he made sure the lady was comfortable. The inflight service was efficient and polite. Overall a good experience other than the concerning check-in.

Aircraft	Boeing 737
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Cork to Luton
Date Flown	August 2024
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Food & Beverages	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

6/10

"Crew were all smiley and pleasant"

41 reviews R G Jackson (Lebanon) 7th August 2024

Trip Verified | My first time flying Ryanair, and despite the dread, it all went very well! I have always avoided it, but as it's the only airline flying from London to Kerry I had no choice. Departure was on-time. Crew were all smiley and pleasant, and the plane itself was clean and comfortable (at least for a one-hour flight). No complaints.

Aircraft	Boeing 737
Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Luton to Kerry
Date Flown	July 2024
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

10/10

"Excellent price/quality ratio"

D Hassen (Belgium) 14th May 2024

Trip Verified | Charleroi- Nimes return. Outbound flight left one minute earlier than scheduled and we arrived ahead of schedule in Nimes. Return flight left with some delay but we finally arrived on time at Charleroi thanks to the 20 minutes they always add to the total flight time. Outbound flight on an old 19yr old plane but new seats were installed so offering a bit more legroom and width. Return on a newer "Boeing Sky Interior" plane which was a nice bonus! Cabin crew on all flights friendly and efficient. Excellent price/quality ratio. No issue at all once more with Ryanair. Would fly them again without hesitation.

Aircraft	Boeing 737-800
Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Brussels Charleroi to Nimes
Date Flown	May 2024
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

6/10

"cheap, safe and efficient"

69 reviews R Darnel (Germany) 5th April 2024

Trip Verified | You get what you pay. Had overweight luggage and had to pay extra, which was processed efficiently at the check in, without too much fuss. Flight was uneventful with kind staff. Yes announcements on Ryanair can be a bit stressful as they have many things to tell and sell you, besides of course safety announcements, but if you bring some headset one can survive it very well. Ryanair is definitely not comfortable flying nor is it luxury, but it is cheap, safe and efficient. Often it is your fellow passengers making the trip worse.

Aircraft	Boeing 737-800
Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Bologna to Cologne
Date Flown	April 2024
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Food & Beverages	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

7/10

"flights were hardly fun"

R Vines (United Kingdom) 10th March 2024

Trip Verified | When things go wrong with low-cost carriers, it can be awful. But I think it is worth saying how well things go most of the time. My return flights from London to Sofia last week cost £62.07, including charges for seats up front, but not priority boarding. The planes were clean and pretty much on time. Not surprisingly, the aircraft were packed, and the flights were hardly fun. But they were less unpleasant than I remember from years ago with Ryanair, when noisy bugle calls and admonitions to buy lottery tickets were among the distractions. If Ryanair would only start selling Champagne on board alongside the Prosecco, I'd be almost happy.

Aircraft	737-8200
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Stansted to Sofia
Date Flown	March 2024
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Food & Beverages	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

10/10

"bang on time and smooth flights"

Andrew Loizou (United Kingdom) 3rd February 2024

Not Verified | Flew back from Faro to London Luton Friday 2nd February. Ryanair in both directions was bang on time and smooth flights in both directions. We always sit in Front for more space and this was very comfortable for just under a 3 hour flight. The cabin crew were polite and efficient with nice sense of humour especially and engagement especially Ethan and his female colleague at the front section. For their human touch [unlike sometimes the stand offish BA crews] merit a 10/10 marking

Aircraft	Boeing 737 900
Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Faro to Luton
Date Flown	February 2024
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Food & Beverages	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

10/10

"Another good affordable flight"

Henry Fenton (United Kingdom) 26th January 2024

Trip Verified | Another good affordable flight with Ryanair. On time, pleasant staff at check-in and on board. We use Ryanair as our first choice on every flight we take.

Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Belfast to Alicante
Date Flown	January 2024
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Food & Beverages	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

10/10

"Really impressed!"

1 review Oliver Rosik (United Kingdom) 20th January 2024

Trip Verified | Really impressed! You get what you pay for, this flight only cost £19.99. The seats were soft, and there was tons of legroom (not in an emergency exit) The cabin was spotless. The colours were a little bright but it was good. Cheap and no frills! Highly recommend, flies almost everywhere.

Aircraft	Boeing 737-800
Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Edinburgh to Paris Beauvais
Date Flown	October 2023
Seat Comfort	★★★★★
Cabin Staff Service	★★★★★
Food & Beverages	★★★★☆
Ground Service	★★★★★
Value For Money	★★★★★
Recommended	

6/10

"a decent offering from Ryanair"

Christopher Rainbow (United Kingdom) 7th January 2024

Trip Verified | I should like to review my flight from Faro to Liverpool with Ryanair. I booked the seat with Ryanair several months before my planned travel and found the website clear and easy to use. Ryanair sent quite frequent emails relating to the flight and attempted to sell me extras. The check-in procedure was followed by a queue drop at Faro Airport. This was not efficient and the app they recommended for speedy bag-drop did not work. Setting that aside, I was able to check-in my bag within less than 30 minutes of having arrived at the airport. Boarding was supposedly via group but this did not materialise at all. The cabin crew had a reasonable presence and delivered a serious safety procedure. During the flight the crew worked hard and had several rounds of drinks for sale. I found the seat suitable for a flight just under 3 hours. The flight departed on-time and arrived on schedule too. Disembarkation was delayed in Liverpool while this was not the fault of Ryanair, there was no communication with the passengers as to why this was the case. Disembarkation was not orderly and was poorly managed. Overall, a decent offering from Ryanair.

Aircraft	Boeing 737
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Faro to Liverpool
Date Flown	January 2024
Seat Comfort	★★★☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★★★☆☆
Food & Beverages	★★★☆☆
Ground Service	★★★☆☆
Value For Money	★★★☆☆
Recommended	

10/10

"cabin crew were welcoming and friendly"

E Brennan (Israel) 6th January 2024

Trip Verified | Flight left the gate ahead of schedule, fare was really cheap and cabin crew were welcoming and friendly. Flight was so much cheaper than Aer Lingus and flying with Ryanair is a much better experience.

Aircraft	Boeing 737-800
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Dublin to Manchester
Date Flown	January 2024
Seat Comfort	★★★★☆
Cabin Staff Service	★★★★★
Ground Service	★★★★★
Value For Money	★★★★★
Recommended	

8/10

"Crew extremely well presented"

Michael Smith (Albania) 6th December 2023

Not Verified | Krakow to Tirana with Ryanair's subsidiary, Buzz, on a brand new Boeing 737Max-200. Flight departed early and arrived before schedule. Crew extremely well presented and professional. Ryanair does not have the most comfortable seats, and leg room is not the best, however for a 1 hour 25 minute flight I do not have much complaints. If you follow their baggage rules and basic online check-in, you won't have any issues. While they are the low cost airline I fly least in comparison to WizzAir/easyJet. I would willingly fly them again if given the opportunity.

Aircraft	Boeing 737Max
Type Of Traveller	Business
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Krakow to Tirana
Date Flown	December 2023
Seat Comfort	★★★★☆
Cabin Staff Service	★★★★★
Ground Service	★★★★★
Value For Money	★★★★★
Recommended	

9/10

"offers fares at great value"

Geoff Bell (United Kingdom) 7th November 2023

Not Verified | Couldn't find any reason to complain. Outbound flight on time, clean aircraft and Cabin Crew friendly and well presented. Great value for money. It was cheaper to fly to Dublin for the day on Ryanair rather than go to London from Bristol for the day by rail. Although the seats do not recline, I thought the leg room was fine. I have flown Ryanair several times over the years and have come to the conclusion that as long as you stick to the rules with regards checking in on line and adhere to luggage sizes, Journeys are hassle free generally. Flight was late on the return leg but they emailed an apology before the dedicated check in time. That didn't bother me personally. Their website is designed to capture more money related to seat allocation, earlier checkin, luggage upgrades, insurance, etc etc but they are optional and as long as you know what you want, there is no obligation to increase the price of your journey. I find their website and online check in very easy to use. I'm a pensioner and I'm grateful Ryanair offers fares at great value.

Aircraft	Boeing 737 800
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Bristol to Dublin
Date Flown	November 2023
Seat Comfort	★★★★☆
Cabin Staff Service	★★★★★
Food & Beverages	★★★★☆
Ground Service	★★★★★
Value For Money	★★★★★
Recommended	

9/10

"Play the game and you'll be fine"

Robin Bramhall (United Kingdom) 2nd November 2023

Not Verified | Play the game and you'll be fine. Got a return flight from Leeds Bradford to Faro for £101. I booked 3 months ahead, didn't reserve a seat, and took only a small bag. Had my boarding pass both on my app, and in paper format (just in case). Took my own food and drink on the plane, didn't buy any of theirs, and didn't buy any of their duty free etc. It really does pay to do your research. At Leeds Bradford someone had lost their boarding pass (I think that cost them £50), while at Faro someone's cabin bag was too big. That had to go in the hold, and I expect that cost him. He said it was OK at Leeds, but maybe he got away with it there. My old bag would have been too big, but I checked Ryanair's website, and bought a new and conforming bag for £9.99. I'm 6 foot tall, and the leg room is tight, but just about OK for a 3 hour flight. The seats were uncomfortable though and needed more cushioning. The outward flight took off and arrived on time. The cabin crew were friendly and efficient. No hard sales pitch for food, drink, duty free. The announcements could have been clearer, but that was down to the Portuguese captain. The return flight was about an hour late taking off, due to delays experienced earlier in the day. This happens. Allow for it. They made up 20 minutes and the plane landed at Leeds Bradford 40 minutes behind schedule. Absolutely no complaints whatsoever and fantastic value for money. I'd reckon that the negative views on here are hugely in the minority. In some cases things have gone wrong, but in others part of the blame must be with the posters who haven't researched and prepared well.

Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Leeds to Faro
Date Flown	October 2023
Seat Comfort	★★★☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★★★★★
Ground Service	★★★★★
Value For Money	★★★★★
Recommended	

10/10

"Well done Ryanair"

C Pascarovic (Belarus) 23rd October 2023

Trip Verified | Took four flights with Ryanair this autumn, Nuremberg to Thessaloniki return and Hahn to Vilnius return. Flawless job. All four flights were pleasantly uneventful, departure and arrival strictly on time (that was especially crucial for me because I needed to take a bus for a consequent journey and a late arrival could be an issue). Very quick check-in and boarding (almost no queues), I'm being amazed with such efficiency of processes again and again. And, of course, really cheap prices (especially to Vilnius, they are even cheaper than bus tickets for the same route, but even to a summer holidays destination which Thessaloniki is, the prices are much more affordable than the competitors' ones). I chose Ryanair many times this year and the company haven't given me any reason to be disappointed so far. Well done Ryanair!

Aircraft	Boeing 737-800
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Frankfurt Hahn to Vilnius
Date Flown	September 2023
Seat Comfort	★★★★☆
Cabin Staff Service	★★★★★
Ground Service	★★★★★
Value For Money	★★★★★
Recommended	

10/10

"delayed for more than 8 hours"

Nils Erik Karlisen (Norway) 21st October 2023

Not Verified | We were delayed for more than 8 hours at Oslo airport, Torp. We filed a complaint and Ryanair contacted me directly with this message and have now paid me more than EUR 500: "7 Oct 2023, 05:51 GMT+1 Dear Nils Erik, Thank you for your reply. We sincerely regret the delay on your flight FR3278 from Oslo Torp to Gdansk on the 12/12/2022. We wish to confirm that a transfer for the sum of 5652.02 NOK (equivalent to 250 EUR per customer and 386 NOK for meal expenses) has been authorised by Ryanair in full and final settlement of your claim under EU261." I am so satisfied with Ryanair for this.

Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Oslo to Riga
Date Flown	December 2022
Seat Comfort	★★★★☆
Cabin Staff Service	★★★★★
Ground Service	★★★★★
Value For Money	★★★★★
Recommended	

7/10

"this trip was pleasantly uneventful"

R Vines (United Kingdom) 23rd September 2023

Trip Verified | People get quite angry about Ryanair, and I can well imagine that if something goes wrong you are really in trouble. But this trip was pleasantly uneventful. So long as you understand the baggage and other rules, and don't (for example) waste money on priority boarding, it can be fine. I paid for a seat at the front, and fast-track security at Stansted. The flights were both about half-an-hour late, but other than that I've no complaints. And there seem to be fewer annoying announcements on board these days.

Aircraft	Boeing 737-8200
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	London to La Rochelle
Date Flown	September 2023
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Food & Beverages	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

8/10

"had no issues with Ryanair so far"

Thomas Desmet (Belgium) 21st September 2023

Trip Verified | Charleroi - Carcassonne return. Both flights landed on time or ahead of schedule. Outbound was with one of their newer B737 MAX planes which offers less engine noise which was nice. Crew on the outbound leg friendly and efficient. Front crew on the return leg looked not motivated and not over friendly overall. Beverage and meal service efficient as always with good selections at ok prices. We have had no issues with Ryanair so far and they are often the only choice for certain destinations if you want a direct flight out of Belgium like in this case. Would still recommend them!

Aircraft	Boeing 737-900
Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Charleroi to Carcassonne
Date Flown	September 2023
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Food & Beverages	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

7/10

"this goes way beyond what is reasonable"

95 reviews Diogo Freitas (Portugal) 11th September 2023

Trip Verified | Ryanair is now obliging passengers who buy airline tickets other than on its own website to go through a complex validation process that involves taking a photograph of their civil identification document (lots of attempts) and a photograph of the passenger's own face! The company always manages to do what it wants without obeying the rules of absolutely every other airline on the market. But I think this goes way beyond what is reasonable. The prices on Ryanair's website are always higher than in some online travel agencies. Very friendly, even charming crew.

Aircraft	Boeing 737-800
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Lisbon to Madeira
Date Flown	September 2023
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

7/10

"Good value for money"

29 reviews C Kamenski (Germany) 11th August 2023

Trip Verified | A pleasant experience. Flight was a little delayed. Staff very attentive and cheerful. Flight was not fully booked, so there was some flexibility with seat choice. Good value for money.

Aircraft	Boeing 737-800
Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Bremen to Chania
Date Flown	August 2023
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Food & Beverages	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

9/10

"hassle free for quick flights around Europe"

E Karouth (Czech Republic) 30th January 2025

Trip Verified | Flew from Prague to Rome Ciampino (return) with both flights spot on time noting that both legs were fully booked without any empty seats onboard. No checked in baggage so headed straight to the gate. The Ryanair mobile App is helpful (apart from the nagging up selling but it's understandable). It's great boarding passes can be saved & viewed in Google Wallet. Boarding was managed well in PRG and CIA even with the full of passengers (with Prague being strict on carry on luggage sizes as some fellow travellers were being a bit cheeky). The cabin crew on my return flight were especially superb and professional with a smile. Both legs were on a Boeing 737-800s (I suspect there are no 737Max stationed in Prague). One had an updated interior with slim seats and notably much more comfortable (esp. Legroom) than the other, although both were in top condition (including cleanliness). This product is ideal + hassle free for quick flights around Europe.

Aircraft	B737-800NG
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Prague to Rome Ciampino
Date Flown	January 2025
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

8/10

"Love Ryanair efficiency"

E Klein (Germany) 26th January 2025

Trip Verified | Love Ryanair efficiency. Does what is says on the packet, nothing pretentious. Crew were great, and even managed to go down with aisle with the trolley on a 30 minute flight. My 7th flight with them, just wish they flew to Frankfurt they'd get all my euro business.

Aircraft	Boeing 738
Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Palma to Barcelona
Date Flown	January 2025
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

10/10

"I wouldn't hesitate to use again"

David Stewart (United Kingdom) 30th December 2024

Not Verified | Flew Ryanair last week to Tenerife. Baggage drop was a breeze as was boarding. Well organised. The flight itself was excellent operated by a fantastic crew especially the cabin manager who was friendly polite and professional. Wouldn't hesitate to use again.

Aircraft	737 800
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Glasgow to Tenerife
Date Flown	December 2024
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Food & Beverages	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

7/10

"good service at a reasonable cost"

R Vines (United Kingdom) 17th November 2024

Trip Verified | I wouldn't want to be a cheerleader for Ryanair. So many things can go wrong. But when things go right, as they did on this trip, I think it should be said that the airline provides a good service at a reasonable cost. Most of the annoying announcements have gone, and by paying a few pounds extra you can get a seat up front and take an extra bag on board. The cabin crew were efficient and friendly, particularly on the return flight, where they were smiling and looked happy to be there.

Aircraft	Boeing 737-800
Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	London Stansted to Biarritz
Date Flown	November 2024
Seat Comfort	☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✓

8/10 "Good value for money"
 1 reviews ✓ Thomas Desmet (Belgium) 6th October 2024
 ✓ **Trip Verified** | Charleroi to Cagliari return. Both planes were operated by Air Malta but in Ryanair colors, featuring the Boeing Sky Interior. Both flights departed on time and arrived before schedule thanks to the extra 15-20 mins most airlines add to their flight schedule. Everything went once more very smooth with Ryanair, as long as you respect their rules which we do. Cabin crew professionally friendly and efficient. Very little info from the flight deck, which we do find a pity. Good value for money. Would (and will) fly with them again without doubt!

Aircraft	Boeing 737-800
Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Charleroi to Cagliari return
Date Flown	October 2024
Seat Comfort	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Cabin Staff Service	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Food & Beverages	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Ground Service	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Value For Money	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Recommended	✓

8/10 "Communication was great"
 9 Bayers (Belgium) 10th September 2024
 ✓ **Trip Verified** | Our flight got at first diverted to Sofia because of bad weather in Podgorica. Luckily, the weather improved and we could fly to Podgorica afterwards, landing with a delay of 3 hours. Communication of Ryanair and the ground throughout the diversion was great. We got frequent updates from the flight deck and via SMS / the app. The whole situation was handled much more appropriately than similar situations I experienced when flying non-lowcost airlines. Only downside was that you still got charged when asking a bottle of water, even after the flight was already delayed with more than 2 hours. But I assume that's the downside of flying low-cost.

Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Brussels to Podgorica
Date Flown	September 2024
Seat Comfort	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Cabin Staff Service	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Ground Service	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Value For Money	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Recommended	✓

6.2. NEUTRAL FEEDBACK SCREENSHOTS

5/10 "cabin crew were friendly and helpful"
 B Shaw (United Kingdom) 1st October 2024
 ✓ **Trip Verified** | Endless queues for boarding at Nice. I had paid for priority boarding but didn't get it. Aircraft full and pretty cramped but cabin crew were friendly and helpful. Ryanair is tolerable for the hour and a half it takes from Stansted to Nice but not for anything longer than a couple of hours.

Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Nice to London Stansted
Date Flown	September 2024
Seat Comfort	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Cabin Staff Service	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Food & Beverages	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Ground Service	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Value For Money	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Recommended	✓

5/10 "no communication from the cockpit"
 69 reviews ✓ B Neumann (Germany) 19th July 2024
 ✓ **Trip Verified** | Black Friday travel, as all computer systems are down, nearly everywhere. So nothing to blame Ryanair here, actually ground staff did really their best with checking in everyone manually. Not an easy task, mainly because of some ignorance and non-understanding from many passengers. Sitting now since more than 1,5 hr in the plane, and we haven't left yet. Also no big deal, with what is going on right now in many European airports, it is understandable and let's hope we will leave anyway. What however is unforgivable is the absolute no communication from the cockpit or from any other staff member regarding the present situation, possible new slot etc. A frustrating silence from the crew, who is of course as well not happy about what is going on. However, a time-to-time human approach is helpful. And of course, as it is ultra low cost, not even a class of water, except numerous (and nerveing) announcements regarding the buy on board whenever we will be at cruising altitude.

Aircraft	Boeing 737-800
Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Cologne to Bologna
Date Flown	July 2024
Seat Comfort	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Cabin Staff Service	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Ground Service	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Value For Money	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Recommended	✗

5/10 "legroom is tiny"
 Joseph Moloney (United Kingdom) 1st June 2024
 Not Verified | Luggage does not get wrecked and also check in is easy including all disabilities like autism like me and my sister. The plane is good, flight is short, security is not as good but decent except at Beauvais. Small amount of luggage. But legroom is tiny and ridiculously bumpy landing. So it's a 5 out of ten.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Birmingham to Beauvais
Date Flown	May 2024
Seat Comfort	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Cabin Staff Service	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Ground Service	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Value For Money	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Recommended	✗

5/10 "was reasonable value"
 S Barton (United Kingdom) 1st June 2024
 ✓ **Trip Verified** | This is a review for a flight with Ryanair from Stansted Airport in the UK to Dortmund in Germany in late May 2024. Credit must be given to Ryanair for their easy to use website and email updates and reminders prior to travel. I had quite an early check-in and found that Ryanair have modernised and automated their check-in at Stanstead. This is welcomed as it certainly made the process quicker. However, I noted 2 elderly people struggling and not one Ryanair staff member had the decency to assist the couple. I spoke to a uniformed staff member who replied with "whatever" when I told her that the couple needed help. I helped them as the staff member literally walked away. Shame on her. Setting the aforementioned aside, boarding was orderly and maybe given the destination of Dortmund the passengers were orderly. The cabin crew included a very friendly Italian lady who helped a young mum with a baby and went out of her way to assist a disabled passenger take her seat. I noted this and thanked the staff member in question when I disembarked. The fare was not the cheapest by any means but was reasonable value. I was overall pleased with this flight with Ryanair. However the ground staff at Stanstead need to be pulled up over the incident I outlined above.

Aircraft	Boeing 737
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	London Stansted to Dortmund
Date Flown	May 2024
Seat Comfort	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Cabin Staff Service	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Food & Beverages	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Ground Service	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Value For Money	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Recommended	✓

5/10 "they are really not better value"
 Peter Loni (United Kingdom) 3rd January 2024
 Not Verified | The flight itself is operated by Malta air and I've always found their cabin crew to be very pleasant and respectful. That however cannot be said for their handling agents either in Pisa or Stansted. The Stansted bunch I have found to be rude, argumentative and hostile. Like they hate their work. Boarding no matter where is a shambles. You're invariably stuck in a freezing cold or roasting hot stailwell even before your aircraft reaches the gate. It's not a pleasant experience. Nowhere to sit. As budget airlines don't use jetties at the gate there is every chance that you're gonna get soaked going to and from the terminal in winter. Cabins are not the worst that I've been on. I'm a wee guy so 2hrs 30mins isn't too bad. As far as cheap fares go, I've yet to get a Ryanair flight that I found to be value for money. All I can say about the flights is that they are generally uneventful and again the Malta Air crew are welcoming. I found that once you add on all of their ridiculous charges they are really not better value than companies like British Airways. It is worth remembering that whether you like Ryanair or not it gives us a choice.

Aircraft	Boeing 737
Type Of Traveller	Business
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Stansted to Pisa
Date Flown	December 2023
Seat Comfort	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Cabin Staff Service	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Food & Beverages	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Ground Service	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Value For Money	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
Recommended	✓

6.3. NEGATIVE FEEDBACK SCREENSHOTS

1/10

"charged to check in at airport"

J Pelle (France) 30th July 2024

Not Verified | Got charged to check in at airport. Apparently I needed to check in online before checking-in at the airport with luggage as well. What is the point of charging 55€ per person to check-in at the airport when I have luggage and need to anyway. Just another way to get extra cash from passengers.

Aircraft	Boeing 737
Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Lisbon to Naples
Date Flown	July 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Cabin Staff Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Ground Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Value For Money	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Recommended	✘

1/10

"fit my backpack in the baggage sizer"

P Peikov (Canada) 24th July 2024

Not Verified | I purchased Priority & 2 Cabin Bags at the time of booking my flight. At the boarding gate the agent asked me to fit my backpack in the baggage sizer. It fitted perfectly, however the agent insisted to remove something to make it smaller. I refused, because the backpack fits inside the sizer and also, there was only one item inside the backpack. Then she promised that I will not fly that day. Her attitude was extremely rude, mean and disrespectful. After all passengers boarded the plane she changed her mind and allowed me to board the plane after paying an extra 75 euro. When complained to Ryanair they answered that there's nothing they can do!

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Sofia to Barcelona
Date Flown	July 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Cabin Staff Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Inflight Entertainment	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Ground Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Value For Money	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Recommended	✘

1/10

"I would avoid at all cost"

C Hales (United Kingdom) 23rd July 2024

Not Verified | On 19th July, there was an IT glitch which impacted severely airlines and other companies. Upon arrival 3hours before our flight, we were asked to queue outside the terminal. Once inside the terminal after 1 hour queue, we asked several times to the ground staff if it was time for check-in. "Sorry I don't have your flight on my list, my manager will let me know". 1 hour before the flight, which means already been queuing for 2 hours, I decided to jump the queue and see what was going on. Ryanair was proceeding with the check-in manually, but there were more than 50 people in front of us. Due to the incompetence and lack of contingency, we missed our flight. Now Ryanair claims this is our fault if we missed the flight. I would avoid at all cost, specially they charge a lot for check-in luggage. Going forward, we will use a shipping company for our luggage, as it is cheaper than flying with them.

Aircraft	Boeing 737
Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Stansted to Krakow
Date Flown	July 2024
Ground Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Value For Money	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Recommended	✘

1/10

"responded that I was late for flight"

R Parfica (Croatia) 20th July 2024

Not Verified | On 19.07.24 due to worldwide IT issues caused by Microsoft updates I could not do online check in for my flight to Dubrovnik. I showed up 4 hours before flight at Stansted airport and had to wait until monitors showed which check in counters to use for my flight. Then I spent 2 hours at check in counters to observe that 1 counter was open with 2 female staff from Ryanair doing manual check in. They did check in for about 10 flights including Dubrovnik. When I realised that I was not getting closer to check in counters and there as just 1 hour and 30 minutes to departure I left check in area and could not return as area was packed. So I proceeded back to hotel and tried to rebook my ticket for 20th. However app and web site was down and could not do it. Contacted Ryanair via chat and staff staid that they cannot do it as system was down. Then I contacted again later Ryanair and asked for refund or to book me for tomorrow (20th) but they responded that I was late for flight and that security at airport was to blame. I waited for 3 hours but simply Ryanair had no staff to work and did not care. Ryanair you should be ashamed for treating your passengers like this. Instead of apology for not being able to handle flights today and offer to move departure tomorrow you just blamed me. This is horrible business practice.

Type Of Traveller	Business
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	London Stansted to Dubrovnik
Date Flown	July 2024
Ground Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Value For Money	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Recommended	✘

1/10

"euros to check in at airport"

Fikret Berkan Anarat (United Kingdom) 19th June 2024

Not Verified | The worst service of airline companies. All other companies close online check-in 2 hours before flight. But this one is one and only unique company to charge you hundreds of euros to check in at airport. And there is no other choice if you arrive airport 3hours before flight. It took me 1hour to reach the desk and because 1hour and 55minutes left to flight, they charge me 110 euros, gave me no other choice to board. This is the first time I am flying with this company and they made no clear instructions of their policy.

Type Of Traveller	Business
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Dublin to Manchester
Date Flown	June 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Cabin Staff Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Food & Beverages	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Inflight Entertainment	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Ground Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Value For Money	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Recommended	✘

1/10

"flight was delayed"

Kristine Zonne (Latvia) 15th June 2024

Not Verified | The flight was delayed. No info on the screen at the airport how long is the delay and what is the estimated departure. Just one word: "Delayed". So we wait and check the Flightradar 24. We could see it is still in the air and that it will be 18 minutes late. No info about that. Still one word. Then we hear the announcement - the boarding starts. No plane yet. We start our way to the boarding. I make a video for my children on the way of the plane moving towards the gates. We arrive at the gates after 5 minutes. Everybody is there. No boarding. And we are told that we are too late. And denied boarding which has not started. No sorry for that they are late. No explanation. It is only our fault. They ask us to leave the boarding area while the people just started to leave the plane. How can you close boarding which has not started yet? This system Ryanair uses often. It is not a one time event. Only you never know when they decide to be mean like that. Sometimes they decide to do the boarding (check the documents) a long time before the plane actually arrives. Sometimes only when it is ready. It is a game they play. So we missed our weekend in Brussels, lost money for the flight and hotel. But we were there before them @ hours before the flight. Strange world, no?

Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Bilund to Brussels
Date Flown	June 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Cabin Staff Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Food & Beverages	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Inflight Entertainment	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Ground Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Wifi & Connectivity	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Value For Money	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Recommended	✘

3/10

"more than ticket price for woman bag?"

Ekaterina Borisova (United Arab Emirates) 5th June 2024

Not Verified | It the first time in Europe when my woman small bag was present on boarding like another bag. I have just a backpack for laptop and small woman bag for normal life. Why I must pay more than ticket price for woman bag? And I not sure that another woman all have just priority and buy an extra baggage. Maybe it's personal for boarding in Prague airport

Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Prague to Gdansk
Date Flown	June 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Cabin Staff Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Food & Beverages	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Inflight Entertainment	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Ground Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Wifi & Connectivity	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Value For Money	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Recommended	✘

1/10

"Flying as little as possible with Ryanair"

Daiva Schaefer (Luxembourg) 4th June 2024

Not Verified | In my opinion and from my experience, Ryanair purposely assigns seats in different rows and at different ends of the airplane for families with children if they do not pay extra. If paying for seats only a few hours before the flight, one can still see many free seats together. Yet, when choosing randomly assigned seats, those will be taken per one free seat from the 2 free seats by each other from the different rows. Why does only the Consumer Rights organization in Spain manage to fight against the airline's practice of charging their customers extra for seating together? Flying as little as possible with Ryanair and every time feel sick about their customer experience.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Charleroi to Kaunas
Date Flown	June 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Food & Beverages	★☆☆☆☆
Inflight Entertainment	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Wifi & Connectivity	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

2/10

"threatened to take us off the flight"

S Rethwell (United Kingdom) 4th June 2024

Not Verified | Absolute JOBSWORTH at gate 83, 8:00am flight to Edinburgh. Had to pay £46 at the gate as our bag "didn't fit" within the correct luggage size. The person who told us this was rude, inconsiderate, would ignore you when suggesting if we could decenter some items into our hold-all bags and he got a HUGE thrill out of doing this. He even threatened to take us off the flight after my partner was getting frustrated because he kept ignoring him when asking what we could do about it? Just be aware - yes it's cheap flights however it all adds up at the end and save yourself the hassle of an absolute idiot trying to charge you more for nothing.

Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Stansted to Edinburgh
Date Flown	June 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"£70 penalty at the gate"

Jaz Uhley (United Kingdom) 4th June 2024

Not Verified | I have flown with this company from LBA on 22 occasions with the same case. This time they charged me £70 penalty at the gate. My case fitted their cage. Had slight bulge because I put my fleece in at the last minute. They told me my case would go in the hold. I have Parkinson's and carry a lot of meds which I why I like them with me. The staff wouldn't listen nor let me remove the fleece or my meds which would have removed the bulge. I had a walking stick and a disability lanyard. Made no difference. Other passengers stuck up for me as I was shaking from the stress. Other larger cases were passing by and they ignored those. But they didn't listen.

Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Leeds Bradford to Alicante
Date Flown	April 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

2/10

"Hopeless service!"

John Gray (United Kingdom) 25th May 2024

Trip Verified | Sitting on the tarmac at Newcastle Airport, time is 7:17 and plane should be taken off at 6:15 ... endless engineers coming onto the plane as theres an issue, poor communication as to why we are waiting to either take off or to empty the plane so we can catch the new one (if there is even one) just announced another engineer is coming to do a 2nd opinion filling me with confidence! Everyone thirsty as its hot but don't worry we are being looked after as its been announced there is water for us to purchase if needed. Time is now 7:21 and an engineer is now going to try and fix the plane and hopefully we will get more news in 30 mins. Hopeless service!

Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Newcastle to Dublin
Date Flown	May 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Food & Beverages	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"lack of responsibility"

Rui Silva (Portugal) 29th April 2024

Trip Verified | It was really bad, after finding out that there were queues of more than two hours to get through security, they didn't care about the passengers, it was still possible to get on the plane but they closed the gates. After 20 minutes passed, they removed the stairs and closed the door. They were not helpful at the door to resolve the problem, they made a corridor for us to go through customs again and took us to the exit of the airport without further helping with rebooking the flight. I ridicule the organization and the lack of responsibility towards customers. Terrible service to society. Foi muito mau depois de sabermos que houve filas de mais de duas horas para passar na segurança eles não quiseram saber dos passageiros, ainda dava para entrar no avião mas fecharam os portões a mentir dizendo que o avião já tinha partido e ainda estava em solo com as escadas de embarque colocadas e toda a segurança. Depois de mais de 20 minutos passados é que tiraram as escadas e fecharam a porta. Não foram prestáveis na porta para resolver o problema fizeram um corredor para passarmos outra vez na alfândega e levaram para a saída do aeroporto sem mais ajudar na remarcação do voo. Estamos a falar que mais de metade das pessoas que viajava no avião não conseguiu embarcar Ainda por cima não se responsabilizam dizendo que é normal e pode demorar a passar na segurança quando relembro que demoraram mais de 2 horas para fazer uma coisa que normalmente não demora mais de 10 minutos. Ridículo a organização e a falta de responsabilidade com os clientes. Pésimo serviço para a sociedade.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Birmingham to Porto
Date Flown	April 2024
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"a classic rip off"

M Kierus (France) 25th April 2024

Trip Verified | We booked a Ryanair flight from Paris Beauvais to Poznan on 21 April 2024. We paid for priority boarding and we also paid for seats, so that our family of 3 could sit together. On the plane we were told that we are not allowed to sit together. The cabin manager (male) was communicating with us in a rude and abusive way. At some point 3 crew members were talking to us at the same time in an extremely insulting manner. The same cabin manager was telling sexist jokes through speakers when selling the perfumes midflight. This is a classic rip off scheme performed by Ryanair. During another flight on the same route on 25 February 2024 we were told that our luggage needs to be taken to the cargo hold underneath the plane, despite the fact that we paid in advance for the carry-on luggage (and priority boarding). The fraud scheme performed by Ryanair is always the same. First, they sell you a service (a seat, a carry-on luggage, etc.) and then they do not fulfill their contractual obligation.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Paris Beauvais to Poznan
Date Flown	April 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"refused to book me onto another flight"

D Blanchet (France) 22nd April 2024

Trip Verified | We all know Ryanair is garbage, but here is another example. They rescheduled my flight, only by two hours, but that makes it impossible for me to take it. They offered to move me to the day before (meaning I lose a day's work, and it costs me a lot) or the day after (when I would have missed my onward travel arrangements). They refused to book me onto another flight later in the month, give me a credit or a refund. Because their T&Cs allow them to reschedule up to 5 hours without compensation.

Type Of Traveller	Business
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Limoges to Manchester
Date Flown	February 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"lost my luggage on a direct flight"

Alan Robinson (Jordan) 8th April 2024

Trip Verified | Ryanair lost my luggage on a direct flight. I still have not received any information. Flight FR 8452 (Charleroi to Amman at 06:30 on the 6th of April, 2024). 1) The flight left approximately 45 minutes late. 2) Finally, the crew informed that the plane was heavy, hence the delay, "but a solution had been found". 3) Upon arrival, my luggage DID NOT ARRIVE. So was the solution removing the luggage of at least a dozen passengers? Looks like we will never know. Ryanair has failed to meet reasonable expectations of checked-in luggage (on a DIRECT FLIGHT) arriving WITH the passengers. I am well aware that at least a dozen more passengers on the same flight were victims of this utter incompetence. I have filed a report in the airport in Amman, filled in all the e-forms, tried the chatbot (useless), chatted to someone in FB Messenger (a waste of time), spoke on the phone to a RA customer service persons in Belgium (who ended up hanging up the call). Three days later, neither I nor the airport in Amman has received any information about the missing luggage.

Type Of Traveller	Business
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Charleroi (Brussels South) to Amman, Jordan
Date Flown	April 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

3/10

"reminds me of late night bus"

Y Chen (Italy) 1st April 2024

Not Verified | Very cheeky check-in system: this did not happen to me but happen to someone queued before me. He missed the online check in window (free online check-in 2 hours before the flight) and was asked to pay £50 to check in. I think he decided to miss the flight. Very dirty seats: my row was full of crisps and the floor had chips and obvious ketchup stains. It reminds me of late night bus. Not what you would expect for an airplane. Poor communication: the flight was delayed for almost an hour, during the whole time there was no explanation. I think passengers deserve to know the reason.

Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Manchester to Milan
Date Flown	March 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Inflight Entertainment	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

5/10

"return to Luton was delayed 4 1/4 hours"

15 reviews Richard Hodges (United Kingdom) 18th March 2024

Trip Verified | Luton to Faro and return Faro to Luton 10 days later. I try not to fly Ryanair, but in this case they flew to the Airport nearest to my accommodation, and at a reasonable (no low cost!) price. Outward flight uneventful - usual cramped and hard seats but at least the third seat unoccupied so some movement possible. No food or drink or scratchcards purchased. The return to Luton was delayed 4 1/4 hours. To Ryanair's credit, we were kept informed by emails at regular intervals - the delay was, apparently, caused by fog or weather of some sort (presumably at Luton). Just as well as no Ryanair support anywhere. So, of course, as it's weather, we aren't entitled to any compensation. Then we get an email saying compensation claims under EU261 must be made via their online form - can't be written, then. We board, and the Captain advises that it was a mechanical fault, and we were in a replacement plane flown from Dublin. So on our return we completed the Ryanair online EU261 claim form, and sent it off. We await a response but are promised one within 7 working days. We shall see. Will I fly Ryanair again? Only if I absolutely can't fly with anyone else.

Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Luton to Faro
Date Flown	March 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"Very bad airline"

G Han (Canada) 16th March 2024

Trip Verified | Very bad airline. I spent 100 pounds check in because I couldn't check in online. Another 70 pounds to check in luggage. However, I don't have time to board the plane in 20 mins because I had to go through a long line of security. In the end, the flight gate was closed, I missed my flight. No money is refunded at all. Not recommended to non European traveller who doesn't know their policies. And it turned out the flight wasn't cheap at all.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Edinburgh to Stansted
Date Flown	March 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"didn't treat my case seriously"

Joanna Krdlak (Poland) 4th March 2024

Not Verified | I contacted Ryanair before my planned flight. The reason I am trying to contact the airline is that because of unforeseen circumstance and sudden surgery I am not able to fly as planned and was urgently transported to Poland. The Ryanair form has the option of refund in case of illness and my illness is also mentioned on the form options but after a long time of contact with Ryanair and explanations and sending the same requests via live chat, emails and form (which eventually didn't work) I managed to get the response from English customer service with the information that I am not eligible to get a refund. I bought a ticket with checked in luggage. I informed the airline immediately but customer service didn't treat my case seriously and it took about a month to get in touch with somebody. Only today when I contacted live chat again I learnt from the consultant that my case is being verified again but the lady said it will be probably negative. In the airline policy it's clearly mentioned that the refund is applicable in certain situations like serious illness and the need of surgery. I sent all the details and doctor opinions and I was informed I can pay a penalty and reschedule a flight for 45 euros. It was not explained why I am not eligible to get a refund despite the fact that the Ryanair's policy is clear. It seems that the Ryanair's policy is not applicable in the same way to all the clients and there's no explanation and contact from the site of the customer service unless you constantly keep trying to ask and send messages. The live chat is also very limited and the consultants say they have no information in this matter. A very bad experience I don't recommend flying with this airline.

Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Lodz to Brussels
Date Flown	August 2023
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"close online checkin 3 hours before"

L Niebuhr (Denmark) 6th January 2024

Not Verified | Booked a flight from Copenhagen to Poland through booking.com. Somewhere in the email from booking.com it states that checkin must be done online from home. I figure I'll do it in the morning since I have plenty of time. It's low season and I don't have any checked in luggage. I live in Copenhagen not far from the airport. Morning comes and I try to check in online. No luck, apparently they close online checkin 3 hours before the flight. I figure I'll just check in at the airport at those self serve terminals. I arrive at the airport 2 hours before my flight and head for a terminal. Prompt says: kindly go to service desk. Head for service desk. They charge me 42 euro to check me in. The flight itself was 57 euro. They almost charged me the price of the flight just to check me in manually! And they forced me to check in manually by closing online and self-serve checkin. This is Ryanair policy. Apparently, Wizzair and booking are not without blame either, as they decide who they want to do business with.

Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Copenhagen to Gdansk
Date Flown	January 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Food & Beverages	★☆☆☆☆
Inflight Entertainment	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Wifi & Connectivity	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"asked me to pay for the backpack"

Pratik Kiri (Australia) 3rd January 2024

Trip Verified | Staff is rude and has no manners. Let alone be professional. I had a backpack with which I flew from Vienna to Paris through Ryanair without any issues. But while flying from Paris to Barcelona, they asked me to pay for the backpack. They have kept a small rack to check size of your carryon baggage, which is way smaller than the one we have in flight and as a result, high chances you will always end up paying. Because of this there was a long queue and one couple even missed their flight and instead of being considerate, they smiled and asked them to purchase ticket for another flight.

Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Beauvais to Barcelona
Date Flown	January 2024
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"ground service staff is really bad"

T Masuner (United Kingdom) 25th December 2023

Trip Verified | Ryanair ground service staff is really bad. If you have a problem, they never listen and they never help. I had problems twice. I tried to explain my situation. They did not listen and they did not take me to the flight. I missed the flight because of their mistake. They did not even look at the evidence that I tried to show them. My family holiday became a tragedy.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Edinburgh to Tirana
Date Flown	December 2023
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"they made us pay a No show fee"

Shabnam Nazari (Germany) 8th December 2023

Not Verified | I wanted to check in online a night before our flight, but my nationality was not listed in their websites and when we wanted to check in in person they asked for a fee, and that still was not a problem! They asked for a credit card to check for late check-in fee, we asked them to pay by our debit card or by cash, but they did not accept it. So we missed our flight, and they made us pay a No show fee on the application so that they give us another flight in the evening. The flight we got was about 30 Euro and the no show fee we paid was 100 Euro. When I told them in Germany we can pay by debit card or cash, they said we are an Irish airline it has nothing to do with Germany! Then why do you have your business here? The other thing is when I mentioned my nationality was not listed on your website they did not accept that and they inserted my nationality manually!

Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Cologne to Palma de Mallorca
Date Flown	November 2023
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"pay if you don't check in online"

R Wang (Singapore) 4th December 2023

Trip Verified | This airline charges you for almost every thing. Every child needs to be seated with an adult. Got it. It is for Safety. But you must pay for the seat selection of the accompanying adult so that you can choose the seat next to the child. Only allowed a bag pack to be carried on for free, any other cabin bag you must pay. You pay if you don't check in online. It's €55 to check in at the airport. That's more than twice of my ticket price. No room for any negotiation. By the way, even if the flight is delayed and you have time to do online check in for free, too bad, just pay. They insisted that we have an email to inform us of this. Too bad if you ignored the email.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Porto to Barcelona
Date Flown	December 2023
Seat Comfort	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Cabin Staff Service	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Ground Service	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Value For Money	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Recommended	✖️

3/10

"At least 5 passengers denied boarding"

95 reviews Diogo Freitas (Portugal) 4th December 2023

Trip Verified | At least 5 passengers denied boarding in Lisbon due to overbooking. In London Stansted the plane was 1:30 minutes late due to what seemed to be defrosting.

Aircraft	Boeing 737-800
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Lisbon to Tirana via Stansted London
Date Flown	December 2023
Seat Comfort	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Cabin Staff Service	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Food & Beverages	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Inflight Entertainment	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Ground Service	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Wifi & Connectivity	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Value For Money	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Recommended	✖️

1/10

"try to avoid it in the future"

5 Peale (Canada) 21st November 2023

Trip Verified | We have a return flight from Gatwick to Alicante. The issue started with online check-in. The application has constantly failed. At the end we make the registration front London to Alicante it was takes a lot of time. Even with this registration we cannot get boarding pass and gave to go to the desk. On the way came back we tried to make check-in online but it always failed. We have to go to the desk and make the registration. The airport charges us 30 euro per person. I tried send my issue to the Ryanair compliance dept, but all of the answers was like "Change device, you have to talk on the chat and etc". Just wanna get back my check-in fee. Nothing, just feeling you talked to a wall. I have very bad experience with the company and will try to avoid it in the future.

Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Alicante to Gatwick
Date Flown	November 2023
Seat Comfort	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Cabin Staff Service	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Food & Beverages	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Inflight Entertainment	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Ground Service	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Wifi & Connectivity	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Value For Money	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Recommended	✖️

1/10

"inside the freezing plane one more hour"

95 reviews Diogo Freitas (Portugal) 5th November 2023

Trip Verified | The duration of this flight is 1h and 20m but we stayed inside the freezing plane one more hour, allegedly not Ryanair's fault but Lisbon's airport. Eventually they turned on the heat when it took off but when approaching Madeira the coldness was back. As usual, dirty plane.

Aircraft	Boeing 737-900
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Lisbon to Funchal
Date Flown	November 2023
Seat Comfort	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Cabin Staff Service	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Ground Service	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Value For Money	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Recommended	✖️

5/10

"flying with Ryanair is a tiring thing"

69 reviews B Acker (Germany) 28th October 2023

Trip Verified | Most importantly Ryanair took me from A to B, safe and in a new plane. However, often flying with Ryanair is a tiring thing. The boarding process can simply be a pain as between scanning your pass and effectively letting you on the plane they let passengers stand in line for long time, often in cramped places. Surely it is to assure everyone is there, can board quickly and enable the closing of the doors of the plane on time, but is quite a torture (many other airlines try to avoid such thing, probably with more differentiation of boarding groups). Furthermore, on this specific flight, the crew truly was a pain trying to sell all kind of "Duty Free" (non existing, as it was a domestic flight) items. The announcements took a full 10 minutes on a 60 min flight (sum it up with the safety instructions, buy on board of catering items, pilot's message(s) etc), reading out all kind of "special offers" for more or less low ranking articles and was loud. Most "refined marketing action" was the seat belts sign to be turned on, for no reason whatsoever (quiet flying conditions), to assure proper sales of articles.

Aircraft	Boeing 737
Type Of Traveller	Business
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Venice to Naples
Date Flown	October 2023
Seat Comfort	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Cabin Staff Service	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Food & Beverages	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Ground Service	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Value For Money	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Recommended	✖️

1/10

"They give flights at good prices"

G Matalone (Spain) 24th October 2023

Not Verified | One of the biggest rip-off companies out there. They give flights at good prices, and then will find any possible way to charge you additional money an make your trip as expensive as possible. Want to cancel your reservation within 24h from the purchase? Not possible. Need some time to choose which luggage you'll need? Be ready to pay double price for that, right after the booking. Want to change your flight? Double price just for the fees. They are tracking everything you do in their app to show you higher prices wherever they can. Customer service replies but doesn't help at all. 100% shameful company.

Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Valencia to Milan
Date Flown	September 2023
Seat Comfort	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Cabin Staff Service	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Food & Beverages	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Inflight Entertainment	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Ground Service	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Wifi & Connectivity	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Value For Money	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Recommended	✖️

2/10

"some leniency should be given"

R Dinur (Israel) 18th October 2023

We flew a few months back to Paphos with **Trip Verified** | Ryanair and we decided to book again for end of October. Unfortunately a war broke out in Israel and the whole world knows what is going on. I spoke to Ryanair Customer Service and explained that with the current situation with friends and family missing we can't possibly go on vacation, and if under the circumstances we can exchange our dates. I was told that the flight has not been cancelled by the airline and therefore we are not eligible for a change or refund. I find this indifference quite appalling from the airline, as no one is cancelling for the sake of it, and under these circumstances some leniency should be given by the company.

Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Tel Aviv to Paphos
Date Flown	April 2023
Seat Comfort	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Cabin Staff Service	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Ground Service	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Value For Money	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Recommended	✖️

1/10

"very unpleasant to deal with Ryanair"

1 reviews B Anderson (United States) 5th October 2023

Trip Verified | I have booked this flight as a part of an itinerary which included various others flights with other airlines. As a last minute situation (unexpected severe health issue) presented itself I had to cancel the whole itinerary and wanted to possibly reschedule the Ryanair flight. To my surprise I was confronted with the unpleasant situation in which there were no reasonable options. For any suggestion I proposed the company had a countermeasure/policy which will not allow me to make a change or if so, at a prohibitive price to the point that it would have been better to simply buy a new ticket. At the end the only option left was to cancel with no refund. It was truly very unpleasant to deal with Ryanair.

Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Bergamo to Kefalonia
Date Flown	September 2023
Seat Comfort	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Cabin Staff Service	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Ground Service	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Value For Money	✖️ 🌟🌟🌟🌟
Recommended	✖️

3/10 "experience was beyond shocking"

Paul Tyrrell (Ireland) 31st December 2024

Not Verified | I have been a long term advocate for this airline. Not after this experience which was beyond shocking. One of the 3 toilets was shut as it contained bags of rubbish from the incoming flight and staff stored additional rubbish in the locked toilet at the rear. Not only grossly inconsiderate but not safe. Access to any toilet was blocked during most of the trolley service leaving long queues to use the only two bathrooms available one of which they then locked because someone had an accident. The conditions young cabin attendants on this flight were expected to work was shameful. If a parent tried to change a nappy of a child it would not have been possible as neither of the bathrooms operating had a child board. The plane was filthy and smell atrocious. Upside an excellent hard working crew.

Aircraft	Boeing 737
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Dublin to Lanzarote
Date Flown	December 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Cabin Staff Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Food & Beverages	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Ground Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Value For Money	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Recommended	✘

3/10 "penalty was due to my not checking in"

Svitlana Oriekhova (Ukraine) 2nd December 2024

Not Verified | I regret choosing Ryanair for my flight from Warsaw Modlin Airport to the Netherlands. Having flown with various airlines for nearly a decade without any issues, my experience with Ryanair has been deeply disappointing. Normally, I purchase my tickets well in advance and receive the necessary information and instructions via email a day before the flight. However, this time was different. Despite booking my ticket as usual, I arrived at the airport two hours before my scheduled flight only to be informed that I could not proceed without paying an additional \$60 fee. I was shocked and utterly confused. When I asked the staff, they were rude, unprofessional, and failed to provide a clear explanation. They repeated that I had no choice but to pay the fee. It turns out this penalty was due to my not checking in manually at least 24 hours in advance, a requirement I was never informed about. This experience has left me extremely dissatisfied with Ryanair, and I will never fly this airline again.

Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Warsaw Modlin to Eindhoven
Date Flown	November 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Cabin Staff Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Food & Beverages	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Ground Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Value For Money	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Recommended	✘

1/10 "does not do refunds or credits"

Christopher Sparrowhawk (United Kingdom) 29th November 2024

Not Verified | They told me I could change my ticket, but Ryanair does not do refunds or credits. I would give them a negative -5 star review if I could. These are the pirates of the sky and now after my last interaction with them. I will never fly Ryanair again. I don't care if it costs me 3 or even 6 times their airfare to fly with anyone else. My mother-in-law has had a major stroke. I have 8 days before I was going on a flight with Ryanair. I spent 45 min waiting for someone to attend to me on the chat (complete waste of my time). So I went to my booking to change the tickets to a later date. The charges to change is more than the tickets I purchased. £45 per flight per change and the difference in the airfare. Now to be clear. I was changing my flight from December 2024 this year to March 2025. It is absolutely criminal and I have had enough. I am sharing this everywhere I can to save others the robbery from rip off artist that is Ryanair.

Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	London Stansted to Dublin
Date Flown	November 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Cabin Staff Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Food & Beverages	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Inflight Entertainment	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Ground Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Wifi & Connectivity	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Value For Money	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Recommended	✘

1/10 "€37 to check in the cabin bag"

Hamdim Tri (Belgium) 19th November 2024

Not Verified | I upgraded my ticket during the booking process to include a cabin bag, paying extra for this service. Additionally, I was aware of the policy stated on the Ryanair website, which mentions that cabin bags may be checked in free of charge if the flight is full, and with my experience with other airlines where I could check in the cabin bag, I brought liquids in my cabin bag. To my surprise, at the counter, I was asked to pay an additional €37 to check in the cabin bag. This seemed unreasonable, especially since I had already paid for it as part of the priority package, which did not provide any tangible benefit. All passengers were still processed in the same flow and stood waiting together, with no apparent priority, in addition to the flight delay. In addition to the bug with the app where I couldn't pay extra for the luggage that should have been checked in for free.

Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Date Flown	November 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Cabin Staff Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Ground Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Value For Money	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Recommended	✘

1/10 "change in name costs £115"

V Mee (United Kingdom) 11th November 2024

Not Verified | A mistake takes place and a booking is made incorrectly. Their app is not working and I can't change the booking within 24 hours of the booking. Contact them and they are asking £93 to apply a change. Just book with an actual airline and do your self a favour. PS: a change in name costs £115!! Changing 7 letters on the system costs more than 2 flights! Absolute thieves.

Type Of Traveller	Business
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Edinburgh to Stansted
Date Flown	November 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Cabin Staff Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Food & Beverages	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Inflight Entertainment	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Ground Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Wifi & Connectivity	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Value For Money	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Recommended	✘

1/10 "legroom is getting smaller"

14 reviews B Aber (Germany) 10th November 2024

Not Verified | Every time they block me after I have made a booking - "Booked through a third party travel agent". Since when is Ryanair dot com a third party agent? And then you can never contact support, you have to go through verification and they keep insisting that the booking was made through a third party agent. There are 2 other things I will continue to complain about: carry-on size limit and legroom. They insist that your personal item has to be tiny, while the space under the seat allows for a much larger bag. And the legroom is getting smaller every year. I'm tall, but I'm also old enough to have stopped growing, and yet the legroom is getting smaller, to the point where I can't fit in the seat. I can only sit sideways, and I'm not even 2 metres tall. Unfortunately, sometimes there is no alternative. The price is no longer low, not really, just sometimes, if your flight is at 6am.

Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Berlin to Sofia
Date Flown	November 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Cabin Staff Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Ground Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Value For Money	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Recommended	✘

2/10 "Totally incompetent"

Ian Handy (United Kingdom) 7th November 2024

Not Verified | Totally incompetent. Delays do happen but failure to communicate and care is at the behest of Ryanair who clearly don't give a monkeys. Only communication given was wrong and annoying based entirely on avoiding compensation. Their marketing strapline is a complete joke. Only positive was the pilot flying fast to avoid flight delay compensation!!

Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Barcelona to Manchester
Date Flown	November 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Cabin Staff Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Food & Beverages	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Ground Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Value For Money	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Recommended	✘

1/10 "Horrible. Absolutely horrible"

Pablo Ayensa (Spain) 6th November 2024

Not Verified | Horrible. Absolutely horrible. I'm a tall man, but no airline was as horrible as Ryanair. There is no legroom, as their specialized 200 aircraft have 20 more seats than a usual aircraft. Cramped as hell inside there. And the seats have so little cushioning that my back hurts. Made me feel sick. Only got this flight because it was the only available. Never again if its possible.

Aircraft	Boeing 737 MAX 8-200
Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Lanzarote to Madrid
Date Flown	November 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Cabin Staff Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Food & Beverages	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Inflight Entertainment	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Ground Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Wifi & Connectivity	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Value For Money	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ ✘
Recommended	✘

1/10

"all of these additional fees"

E Valderna (United States) 4th November 2024

Trip Verified | If there were ever a competition amongst airlines for worst value, Ryanair would take the crown. Consistently horrible experience with rude staff and overall quality. I understand that they are popular because of low prices, but in the end I doubt they actually offer the best prices after accounting for all the extra fees. After considering all of these additional fees charged on top of their standard fees, the cost is basically a premium economy class with a regular airline.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Funchal to Paris
Date Flown	November 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Cabin Staff Service	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Food & Beverages	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Inflight Entertainment	✘ ✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Ground Service	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Value For Money	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Recommended	✘

1/10

"Ryanair are stressful"

George A Chantry (United Kingdom) 1st November 2024

Trip Verified | I arrived at exactly 1hr and ten minutes before the advertised flight departure time on a delayed flight at the bag check-in automated machines and by forty minutes before the original departure time. I was charged £75 for a late bag check in even though the flight was delayed. Ryanair are stressful. I recommend Wizz air to all Ryanair customers reading this who fly from Luton direct to Warsaw chopin. The ryanair automated bag check in did not work and would not scan my boarding card. The automated bag machine did not work. I was told they should have opened the bag check-in for me manually because the flight was delayed and I had arrived on time at the automated check in for a delayed flight, but they refused to open the bag check in.

Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Premium Economy
Route	Stansted to Warsaw Modlin
Date Flown	November 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Cabin Staff Service	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Ground Service	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Value For Money	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Recommended	✘

1/10

"never spend a single cent on Ryanair again"

1 reviews L van den Bos (Ireland) 26th October 2024

Trip Verified | I was with my wife and 22-month-old daughter at the gate on my return flight back home from Amsterdam. I had no trouble on the way in. We checked in our bags in Dublin, and they didn't spot a thing. We got through at the gate in Dublin, no problem. Nor did they see anything wrong when we checked in our bags on our way back in Amsterdam. But then we arrived at the gate and apparently there was something wrong with my name on my boarding pass. It didn't match with my passport. And it's true it didn't match. And they couldn't let me through unless I did a name change for €160 euro. For an administrative issue that wasn't an issue on three occasions before. But if it was the only way, then let's get with it. And so I took out my card and was ready to pay and although the guy advised me this was the only way, he was unable to get it done. On the phone (with whoever), time was ticking along until time was no more. And we were denied to board. I made a vow never to spend a single cent on Ryanair again.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Amsterdam to Dublin
Date Flown	October 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Cabin Staff Service	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Ground Service	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Value For Money	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Recommended	✘

1/10

"never fly with Ryanair again"

Jelena Kadovic (Australia) 19th October 2024

Trip Verified | Upon arrival at the airport, the ground staff at the check-in informed me the flight was overbooked and there are no available seats, irrespective of having a valid ticket. My 2 sisters and myself were told to go to the gate and wait to find out if there are empty seats after the gate closes. We were not the only people in this situation at the gate, there were at least 2 more people. The family of 5 was late at the gate by 10 seconds and we were "given" their seats: the ground staff let us on the plane in front of the devastated family. The time spent at the gate waiting for the seats that belong to us was very stressful and humiliating. This company sells double tickets and hopes for passengers not to fly or be late at the flight. This wasn't an unfortunate situation, but the way they operate the business. Ryanair even published a policy to justify this behavior, which is completely unacceptable. This was the worst travel experience in my life and I will never fly with Ryanair again.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Tirana to Paris
Date Flown	October 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ 🗳️
Cabin Staff Service	✘ ✘ ✘ ✘ 🗳️
Ground Service	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Value For Money	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Recommended	✘

1/10

"just fobbed us off"

J Basayan (United Kingdom) 10th October 2024

Trip Verified | My son is 10 with a hidden Disability. We had exit seats booked. A child cant sit on exit seats so asked crew to move seats. Son was wearing his sunflower lanyard but crew ignored this and asked to sit him (10 year old with Autism) alone. I told the crew he has a lanyard to make them aware he has a hidden disability. They replied "Dont be rude" to me only due to me making them aware he has a disability! We then moved seats and sat down quietly. After we sat down one of the crew shouted loudly "We still have time to kick them off the plane" as she walked off to show off her ego. This is how Ryan Air Treated my 10 year old Autistic Boy for no good reason at all. I made a complaint and they replied by saying they acknowledge their crew were "discourteous" and "could have handled it better" No apology at all and just fobbed us off. Ryan Air claim to be part of the sunflower lanyard network to recognise and assist passengers with hidden disabilities. The reality is they acted with impunity with my child and treated him very badly.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Tirana to Stansted
Date Flown	September 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Cabin Staff Service	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Ground Service	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Value For Money	✘ ✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Recommended	✘

2/10

"stood out for its lack of consideration"

Rian Maia (Ireland) 9th October 2024

Not Verified | This is to share my recent experience on flight FR 3103 from Amsterdam to Dublin on 08/10/2024, which was delayed by approximately 30 minutes. During the flight, I inquired with a staff member about the possibility of moving to an available seat beside my partner. He informed me that the flight was full, and his demeanor suggested a level of disdain. Shortly thereafter, another staff member mentioned that there were indeed two seats available at the front but advised me to wait until everyone had settled in. I patiently waited and approached the spare seats only to find that the initial staff member was waiting for me to sit down and settle in to only after inform me that I could only swap seats after takeoff. Keep in mind that there were spare seats because someone had already moved to a different location in the aircraft. In the meantime, many passengers were also swapping seats without issue, which left me confused as to why I was singled out. The staff member appeared indifferent to the situation, merely observing the aisle without intervening. Additionally, I noted at least seven empty seats near my location, which raises concerns about whether he properly assessed the situation. I have flown with Ryanair multiple times, and while I have encountered issues before, this experience stood out for its lack of consideration. I would like to express my appreciation to the colleague who attempted to assist me, it would be beneficial for your company to have more staff members like him.

Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Amsterdam to Dublin
Date Flown	October 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ ✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Cabin Staff Service	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Inflight Entertainment	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Ground Service	✘ ✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Wifi & Connectivity	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Value For Money	✘ ✘ ✘ 🗳️ 🗳️
Recommended	✘

1/10

"Very poor service"

Jeff Tegart (Ireland) 5th October 2024

Trip Verified | Very poor service from Ryanair as usual. Flights delayed by over an hour and a half on both legs of my journey miss connecting transport so cost 130euro for taxi. Staff are rude and unhelpful with one staff member become angry and aggressive. Very unpleasant experience and will avoid in the future.

Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Dublin to Barcelona
Date Flown	October 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Cabin Staff Service	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Food & Beverages	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Ground Service	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Value For Money	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Recommended	✘

1/10

"a huge additional baggage fee"

Catherine Chen (United States) 30th September 2024

Not Verified | I paid for their upgrade baggage allowance and priority boarding. However, even though there were no issues on previous Ryanair flights, they said the same bag today was oversized because a little piece of the wheel stuck out and then extorted a huge additional baggage fee, essentially doubling the fare. In addition, the boarding process was beyond chaotic and takeoff was over an hour late. And the seat on the plane was filthy. There were food crumbs all over the seat and sticky residue on the tray table. To call this airline an embarrassment would be a gross understatement!

Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Manchester to Berlin
Date Flown	September 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Cabin Staff Service	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Ground Service	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Value For Money	✘ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️ 🗳️
Recommended	✘

1/10

"Absolute chaos"

W Dale (United Kingdom) 30th September 2024

Trip Verified | Absolute chaos. We were made to stand for ages in the queue at the gate. In spite of having priority boarding, the staff decided to let everyone pile on at the same time. We were then made to stand on the tarmac (thankfully it was a warm day and not raining) for nearly an hour due to the flight being late and having to get the plane cleaned. Staff were completely uninterested and look bored for the duration of the flight. Glad we had had lunch beforehand because the prices for anything on board was through the roof and just there to rip you off due to being a captive audience. Plus you have to order via QR code, which is pointless because you have to put your phone in flight mode and there's no wi-fi on board. Flight was cramped and the ventilation didn't work, so everyone in the cabin was hot and uncomfortable. Both of us ended up with banging headaches after the flight. This was my husband's first and last time flying with Ryanair, and we've both said never again!

Aircraft	Boeing 787
Type Of Traveller	Couple Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Stansted to Berlin
Date Flown	September 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"left stranded at the airport"

A Demetris (Cyprus) 29th September 2024

Trip Verified | Terrible customer service I am writing to formally complain about our recent experience during our return flight from Krakow to Paphos on September 24, 2024. We had traveled to Krakow just four days prior with the same carry-on bags without issue. However, at the airport during our return, a rude employee singled out my wife and me, claiming our carry-on bag was oversized and demanding additional payment. Despite my attempts to explain that the bag had previously been accepted, the employee was unhelpful and escalated the situation by calling security. As a result, we missed our flight and were left stranded at the airport. This experience was not only frustrating but also embarrassing and unacceptable, especially considering we had paid for priority boarding.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Krakow to Paphos
Date Flown	September 2024
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"Terrible terrible service"

J Alvarez (Spain) 27th September 2024

Trip Verified | The flight was as always delayed. I don't remember the moment when Ryanair departs on time. The worst thing is that they even don't notify you in advance for at least 2 hours (when they definitely know that flight will be delayed) to give you opportunity to spend this waiting time at home or in a city. No you come to airport to spend 1.5 additional hours in the overwhelmed airport and then 30 minutes inside the plane. Always the same tricks to not pay customers for delays. Terrible terrible service.

Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Valencia to Vienna
Date Flown	September 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"staff seem completely uninterested"

E Dalmare (Spain) 23rd September 2024

Trip Verified | Ryanair is hands down the worst airline I've ever had the misfortune of flying with. From the moment I stepped on board, I felt like I was being herded like cattle. The seats are cramped, uncomfortable, and have the legroom of a shoebox. There's lots of hidden fees. They charge you for everything — bags, choosing a seat, breathing, it feels like! The staff seem completely uninterested in helping, and the whole experience felt like they just want to squeeze as much money out of you as possible while offering the bare minimum in return. Delays are basically guaranteed, and good luck trying to get any compensation or even a decent explanation. Honestly, I'd rather swim to my destination next time! Avoid Ryanair if you value your sanity.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Edinburgh to Dublin
Date Flown	September 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"I was charged for my handbag"

Stefan Irimicuc (Romania) 22nd September 2024

Not Verified | Would not recommend to my worst enemy. The flight was delayed an hour, the ticket check and boarding was done in a small place with terrible crowded. Bonus I was charged for my handbag for being "too big". Also when paying the guy put the wrong dates from my card and told me that the payment was rejected like it was my fault that he cannot read. And by the way he was obviously having trouble reading!

Type Of Traveller	Business
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Luton to Brugas
Date Flown	September 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Food & Beverages	★☆☆☆☆
Inflight Entertainment	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Wifi & Connectivity	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"huge additional baggage fee"

Jeevan Perera (United States) 9th September 2024

Trip Verified | I paid for their upgrade baggage allowance and priority boarding and even though there no issues on the flight inbound, they said the same bag on return was oversized because a little piece of the wheel stuck out and then extorted a huge additional baggage fee.

Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Dublin to Manchester
Date Flown	September 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"bags took over 2 hours"

Zack Rogers (United Kingdom) 1st September 2024

Not Verified | Absolutely useless 4 baggage handlers in Birmingham airport I am told to unload all the planes. The bags took over 2 hours for the bags to get into the bagging hall. My 9 year old daughter sitting in the floor at 3.14am. My son waiting around to pick us up in Birmingham. (we live over 20 miles away). Useless staff. Nobody to talk to. No customer services. Just absolutely useless. If you can not look after your customers they will leave. Ryanair can only have the monopoly for so long. Let's face it you competitors could not do a worse job! Staff the airline to deliver the service we pay for. Also look into Swissport! It is a shame there are not more airlines we can use, to fly out to the destinations we want to go to. Seems like you don't need to look after your customers if they have limited choice of where to go! Shame on you.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Malta to England
Date Flown	September 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"bag was too large and demanding payment"

Cheung Wong (United Kingdom) 31st August 2024

Not Verified | I had the worst experience with them. I only had a small bag and had no problems getting on the plane in the UK, no one said anything about the bag. Then when I was coming back from Berlin I was made to feel like a terrible person with two people saying my bag was too large and demanding payment. This is despite the fact that they had already let people through with similar sized backpacks. I felt victimised as a solo female traveller and felt the only thing I could do was pay if I wanted to get home. The behaviour of the staff was appalling, and I would not recommend Ryanair to anyone. Sometimes it's not about the money, it's about customer service and decency, none of which I received from Ryanair in Berlin. If they provide good service it might be different matter but this is the worst service I've ever received.

Aircraft	Boeing 737 max 8
Type Of Traveller	Solo Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Berlin to Manchester
Date Flown	August 2024
Seat Comfort	★☆☆☆☆
Cabin Staff Service	★☆☆☆☆
Food & Beverages	★☆☆☆☆
Ground Service	★☆☆☆☆
Value For Money	★☆☆☆☆
Recommended	✘

1/10

"Disdain for passengers"

G Nowak (Poland) 9th August 2024

Trip Verified | Worst airline I've ever used. Flight FR 954 from Palma Mallorca to Poznań. 24 hours of delay. Disdain for passengers, especially with small kids. No info, no care, just pure malfunction. Terrifying experience. Please don't give them your money.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Palma to Poznań
Date Flown	August 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ (1/5)
Cabin Staff Service	✘ (1/5)
Ground Service	✘ (1/5)
Value For Money	✘ (1/5)
Recommended	✘

2/10

"flight delayed by 10 hours"

Sergio De Araujo (United States) 5th August 2024

Not Verified | The flight was delayed by 10 hours without any explanation, and every two hours, the flight would keep getting pushed back. Worst company I have ever flown with.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Barcelona to Edinburgh
Date Flown	August 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ (1/5)
Cabin Staff Service	✘ (1/5)
Food & Beverages	✘ (1/5)
Ground Service	✘ (1/5)
Value For Money	✘ (1/5)
Recommended	✘

1/10

"my immense dissatisfaction"

Tigran Akopyan (Czech Republic) 3rd August 2024

Not Verified | I want to express my immense dissatisfaction with Ryanair regarding the recent experience I had with them. Our flight to Prague, originally scheduled to depart at 5:55 AM, has been delayed for an astonishing 16 hours, with the boarding time constantly being pushed back. This is completely unacceptable. Throughout this ordeal, the service provided by Ryanair has been atrocious. Passengers were fed cheap sandwiches all day long. To my disbelief, the airline offered a pork sandwich to my one-year-old daughter, which is highly inappropriate and inconsiderate. Families, including ours, were left to sleep on the floor or outside on the ground around the airport. Passengers with disabilities were left sitting in their wheelchairs for extended periods without any proper assistance. This level of service is beyond unacceptable and I firmly believe that Ryanair deserves a special award for the worst service in the industry. I will never fly with Ryanair again and will strongly recommend to everyone I know to avoid this airline at all costs. If Ryanair's management ever had to endure 16 hours sitting outside, eating terrible sandwiches, and subjecting their children to such conditions, they might understand the sheer disrespect and disregard for passenger comfort and well-being that we experienced.

Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Zadar to Prague
Date Flown	August 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ (1/5)
Ground Service	✘ (1/5)
Value For Money	✘ (1/5)
Recommended	✘

1/10

"Misleading airline"

A Dimou (Cyprus) 30th July 2024

Trip Verified | Misleading airline - cheap flight ended up costing much more! Went to the gate with my cabin bag checked in bag paid online and the airport staff told me I have to pay a penalty of EUR 65 and by proceeding with an online claim assured me I was going to get the penalty back as it happens often and this is a usual process, which I didn't! The issue is that I pay for the penalty but the cabin bag finally ended traveling as a cargo as 'originally' paid.

Aircraft	Boeing 747
Type Of Traveller	Family Leisure
Seat Type	Economy Class
Route	Mykonos to Paphos
Date Flown	July 2024
Seat Comfort	✘ (1/5)
Cabin Staff Service	✘ (1/5)
Ground Service	✘ (1/5)
Value For Money	✘ (1/5)
Recommended	✘